

Unix timestamp conversion

The log event will be recorded with a Unix timestamp by Pynput. Before copying the Unix timestamp into MS Excel, ensure that scientific notation is disabled. Then, use the following formula to convert the Unix timestamp to Excel time and display it in the "m/d/yyyy h:mm:ss.000" (Custom format):

1. **Disable scientific notation in Excel preferences.**
2. **Paste the 13-digit Unix timestamp (milliseconds, 10 digits for seconds) into cell A1.**
3. **In cell B1, use the following formula to format the Unix timestamp correctly:**
`=LEFT(A1,10) & "." & RIGHT(A1,3)`
4. **In cell C1, use the following formula to convert the timestamp to Excel time format:**
`=(((B1/60)/60)/24)+DATE(1970,1,1)`